

STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF FERRIC ARSENITE AND
FERROUS ARSENATE. PART II. COMPOSITION OF THE
SO-CALLED FERRIC ARSENITE (PRODUCT OF
MIXING FeCl_3 AND NaAsO_2)

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When aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite are mixed together at high concentrations, a mixture of arsenite and arsenate of iron with some free ferric oxide and adsorbed arsenite is obtained. At low concentration of the reactants, arsenate is completely eliminated, although ferrous iron remains in the compound in appreciable amounts. When aqueous ferric chloride is mixed with neutralised sodium arsenite, the resulting compound retains arsenate in high and low concentrations of the reactants. When aqueous ferric chloride and neutralised sodium arsenite are mixed and the mixture aged for a month, the total quantities of arsenic and iron reach almost a constant limit at all dilutions. When ferric chloride is added more than its equivalent amount to sodium arsenite, a colloidal solution is obtained. When this solution is dialysed for a few weeks, the sample of the product gets completely freed from arsenate and tends to reach a constant composition corresponding to $\text{Fe}(\text{AsO}_2)_3$, $2\text{-}3\text{ Fe}_2\text{O}_3$.

In the light of the observations made in Part I of the series of papers (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 47) quantitative analyses were carried out elaborately in order to throw some light on the composition of iron arsenite and arsenate. In this paper the composition of the product of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite only has been discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The analyses of the products obtained by mixing the reactants under several conditions of concentration, dilution and neutrality were mainly directed to the estimations of Fe^{+++} , Fe^{++} , AsO_4^{--} and $(\text{AsO}_2)^-$ in the compound. The samples were prepared by mixing standard solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite. The precipitates became colloidal on washing, and therefore it was not possible to ensure complete removal of the associated products, by washing over a Bucher funnel. First of all total quantities of iron and arsenic were estimated, then Fe^{+++} , Fe^{++} , $(\text{AsO}_2)^-$ and $(\text{AsO}_4)^{--}$ were estimated by the methods detailed below.

Estimation of total Fe and As.—A weighed quantity of the sample (0.3 to 0.4 g.) was taken in a beaker and dissolved in a few c. c. of conc. hydrochloric acid (Merck's). The solution was reduced completely by sulphur dioxide so that all arsenate may be reduced to arsenite and ferric to ferrous. Excess of sulphur dioxide was boiled off and then hydrogen sulphide was passed into the solution to precipitate arsenic as As_2S_3 . Excess of hydrogen sulphide was removed by bubbling CO_2 . The precipitated sulphide was filtered in a Gooch crucible, and washed with hot water till free from iron and chloride. As_2S_3 was dried at 105° and weighed as usual.

The filtrate was then collected from the filter flask, concentrated by evaporation and estimated as Fe_2O_3 after oxidising it with strong HNO_3 . From this total iron was calculated.

Estimation of Fe^{+++} and Fe^{++} in the samples of Ferric Arsenite.—This was done by matching the intensity of colour by means of a Nephelometer. This instrument was corrected for its zero error. A very dilute solution of ferric chloride, to which a drop of KCNS solution was added, was taken as standard to compare its intensity of colour with that of the ferric arsenite solution of comparable strength in hydrochloric acid. The result was obtained by applying the relation $M_1/M_2 = h_2/h_1$, where M_1 and M_2 are the amounts of ferric chloride in the standard FeCl_3 (N/2490) and in the sample solution, and h_1 and h_2 are the height of the standard FeCl_3 and ferric arsenite solution, each coloured with a drop of KCNS solution. Thus the amount M_2 of the ferric iron in the arsenite was obtained, M_1 , h_1 and h_2 being known. Subtracting the amount of ferric, determined colorimetrically from the total iron already estimated, the quantity of Fe (ous) iron present in the compound was known.

Estimation of AsO₄^{'''} in the Samples.—Quantity of arsenate was determined by subtracting the estimated quantity of arsenic as AsO₂' from total arsenic already determined. It was confirmed by control experiments that potassium permanganate reacted quantitatively with an acidified solution of sodium arsenite at about boiling temperature and the result so obtained was identical with that determined by iodometry. Therefore, a weighed quantity of ferric arsenite was dissolved in excess of dilute H₂SO₄ and titrated in sufficiently hot solution against a standard solution of potassium permanganate. The titre values of potassium permanganate corresponded to the quantities of AsO₂', Fe^{'''} and chloride which were present in the sample. The quantities of Fe^{'''} and Cl['] being known, AsO₂' could be calculated.

Estimation of Chloride associated with Ferric Arsenite.—A weighed quantity of the sample was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and an excess of standard solution of AgNO₃ was added and the precipitate of AgCl was left overnight. The residual AgNO₃ was titrated against standard KCNS solution, the ferric salt already present acting as an indicator.

Percentage composition of each sample of the product was thus determined and the simplest molecular formula of each was calculated from the quantities of ferric, ferrous, AsO₂' and AsO₄^{'''} to the nearest whole number.

TABLE I

	Total Fe.	Fe ^{'''}	Fe ^{''}	Total As.	AsO ₂ '	(AsO ₄) ^{'''}	NaCl.
1. M/1.3-FeCl ₃ + M/1.24-NaAsO ₂ (aq. solns.)	24.39%	19.24%	5.15%	43.78%	56.26%	8.04%	1.22
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{5.25} Fe ^{''} _{1.4} (AsO ₂) ₈ (AsO ₄)						
2. M/5-FeCl ₃ + M/5-NaAsO ₂ (aq. solns.)	26.67	21.96	4.71	43.02	60.78	0.87	0.46
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{5.5} Fe (AsO ₂) ₈ (AsO ₄) _{0.1}						
3. M/10-FeCl ₃ + M/10-NaAsO ₂ (aq. solns.)	27.30	24.01	3.29	41.89	59.95	Nil	0.40
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{7.3} Fe ^{''} (AsO ₂) _{9.5}						
4. M/25-FeCl ₃ + M/25-NaAsO ₂ (aq. solns.)	28.37	25.42	2.95	37.32	53.73	Nil	0.31
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{8.8} Fe (AsO ₂) _{9.5}						
5. M/50-FeCl ₃ + M/50-NaAsO ₂ (aq. solns.)	29.56	27.55	2.01	35.93	51.68	Nil	0.48
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{13.7} Fe ^{''} (AsO ₂) _{13.5}						

TABLE II

	Total Fe.	Fe ^{'''}	Fe ^{''}	Total As.	AsO ₂ '	(AsO ₄) ^{'''}	NaCl.
1. M/1.3Aq. FeCl ₃ + M/1.2-neutralised NaAsO ₂	19.37%	11.51%	7.86%	42.35%	50.40%	13.01%	15.91%
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{1.9} Fe ^{''} _{1.3} (AsO ₂) ₄₄ (AsO ₄)						
2. M/5-Aq. FeCl ₃ + M/5-neutralised NaAsO ₂	23.26	21.40	1.86	40.66	56.94	3.08	7.79
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{15.3} Fe ^{''} _{1.3} (AsO ₂) _{21.3} (AsO ₄)						
3. M/10-Aq. FeCl ₃ + M/10-neutralised NaAsO ₂	25.05	22.46	2.59	37.27	49.87	4.28	8.59
	Empirical formula : Fe ^{'''} _{11.5} Fe ^{''} _{1.3} (AsO ₂) _{13.4} (AsO ₄)						

TABLE III

(Sample prepared by ageing)

	Total Fe.	Fe ⁺⁺⁺	Fe ⁺⁺	Total Fe.	AsO ₂	AsO ₄	NaCl.
1. <i>M</i> /1.3-Aq. FeCl ₃ + <i>M</i> /1.3 neutralised NaAsO ₂	21.13%	16.74%	4.39%	38.55%	49.41%	7.26%	12.18%
	Empirical formula : Fe ⁺⁺⁺ ₅ -Fe ⁺⁺ _{1.3} (AsO ₂) _{7.8} (AsO ₄)						
2. <i>M</i> /5-Aq. FeCl ₃ + <i>M</i> /5-neutralised NaAsO ₂	20.99	15.24	5.74	40.55	50.54	9.05	10.54
	Empirical formula : Fe ⁺⁺⁺ ₅ -Fe ⁺⁺ _{1.5} (AsO ₂) _{7.3} (AsO ₄)						
3. <i>M</i> /10-Aq. FeCl ₃ + <i>M</i> /10-neutralised NaAsO ₂	21.99	17.44	4.55	38.96	49.79	7.52	7.34
	Empirical formula : Fe ⁺⁺⁺ ₅ Fe ⁺⁺ _{1.3} (AsO ₂) _{7.8} (AsO ₄)						

DISCUSSIONS

The results of the analyses of the samples obtained by mixing FeCl₃ and NaAsO₂ give the following interesting observations :—

(a) When aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite are mixed together, arsenite and arsenate are formed only in higher concentrations of the reactants (Table I.)

(b) When aqueous solution of ferric chloride is mixed with neutralised solution of sodium arsenite, the resulting compound contains both arsenite and arsenate, at high and low concentrations of the reactants (Table II).

(c) When aqueous solution of ferric chloride is mixed with neutralised solution of sodium arsenite, and the mixture is allowed to age for a month, the total quantity of iron and arsenite in the samples tends to approach a limit. (Fe, 21.5%, AsO₂, 50.0%, vide Table III.).

(d) When ferric chloride is added in excess to sodium arsenite, a colloidal solution is formed, which leaves only ferric arsenite on dialysis in the samples, and no excess or free arsenite or arsenate is obtained in the dialysed samples.

(e) Percentage of total iron increases with dilution of the reactants when they are mixed in equivalent proportion (Table I and II). But when the mixed reactants are subjected to ageing, this is not the case. In Tables I and II, it will be further observed that the percentage of total arsenic decreases as the concentration of the reactants is increased, but it does not vary so regularly in the process of ageing or dialysis (Tables III and IV).

Combining all these observations, it can be taken as an established fact that the combination of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite is initiated by mutual oxidation and reduction of the reactants. The ultimate composition of the product depends much on the neutral, acid or alkaline character of the medium. In acidified solutions of ferric chloride, colloidal precipitate is formed which, by dialysis, is reduced to the composition Fe (AsO₂)₃, x Fe₂O₃.

The analytical results suggest that the composition of the precipitated compound is very much influenced by its hydrolytic and adsorptive properties. Hydrolysis of the compound is supported by the observation that the proportion of iron increases with dilution of the reactants (Tables I and II). The ferric hydroxide formed by hydrolysis remains with the compound, while free arsenious acid is partly washed off into the filtrate in spite of its low solubility. Arsenic acid formed by mutual oxidation and reduction of the reactants or by the hydrolysis of ferric arsenate, is easily washed out, and hence the samples are free from arsenate at higher dilutions. It is well known that ferric hydroxide adsorbs arsenious acid. Bunsen and Berthold ("Das Eisenhydroxyd", 1834) observed that ferric hydroxide had a great power of adsorbing arsenious acid, and considered that basic ferric arsenate was formed. Bitty (*Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3181) observed that adsorption of arsenious acid by ferric hydroxide follows the well known equation $x/m/KC^n$. Hence, there is a great probability of some arsenite remaining adsorbed in the samples of ferric arsenite, the extent of which is difficult to ascertain from the empirical formulae obtained from quantitative analysis, or percentage composition.

Sen (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **31**, 419) showed that ageing had an appreciable effect on the adsorptive power of ferric hydroxide, and the amount of adsorbed arsenious acid is considerably decreased on ageing. The percentage of arsenious acid in the samples prepared by ageing method is almost constant (Tables III). This may be attributed to the ageing effect on the adsorption of free arsenious acid which may decrease to a constant value for samples prepared under the same conditions and may yield a compound having practically the same composition. The empirical formulae of the samples (Table III) suggest this.

The maximum role of hydrolysis and complete elimination of free arsenious acid and arsenic acid are observed when colloidal solutions of the product are prepared by mixing excess of ferric chloride with aqueous or neutral solution of sodium arsenite, and the mixture is dialysed for several weeks. The composition of the samples leads to a basic compound $\text{Fe}(\text{AsO}_2)_3 \cdot 2\text{-}3\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (Table IV).

Although the quantitative estimations of the samples prepared by mixing ferric chloride with aqueous and neutral solutions of sodium arsenite have given a clear evidence of the formation and presence of Fe^{II} and AsO_4^{IV} during the precipitation of the compound, yet it was not possible to determine the exact proportions of ferric arsenite, ferrous arsenate, ferrous arsenite, and ferric arsenate which might have been simultaneously formed. We can, at best, derive an empirical formula. It may further be observed that hydrolysis and adsorption effects which considerably influence the composition of the precipitate, are responsible for the variations in the empirical formulae determined from the analytical results.

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